

Title: Facilitation Guide for Student-led Discussion and Participation Evaluation Rubric

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Audience: Middle School, High school, College, Graduate School

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Learning Material Type: Discussion guide, rubric, case study examples

Short Description -

The Facilitation Guide for Student-led Discussion and Participation Evaluation Rubric provide structured guidelines for effective class discussions of case studies/scientific reports and transparent evaluation of participation by both the student (self-evaluation) and the instructor. Discussions are conducted in a student-led format. Instructors act to provide additional clarity, address misconceptions, and gently guide focused conversation to maximize participation and achieve learning objectives. This approach emphasizes active learning, encourages peer engagement, and supports critical thinking skills. The participation rubric is provided to facilitate transparent grading, encourage self-evaluation and support student metacognitive awareness. This resource is adaptable across disciplines, course levels, and instructional modalities, and is intended to support equitable, consistent, and meaningful assessment of discussion-based learning. A structured manual for in-class discussions, the self-evaluation rubric, and STEM-focused case study examples are provided in this resource.

MERLOT Resource Summary (Abstract) - (150–250 words)

The Facilitation Guide for Student-led Discussion and Participation Evaluation Rubric provide structured guidelines for effective class discussions of case studies/scientific reports and transparent evaluation of participation. Students are provided in advance with assigned material that details the in-class discussion framework including a curated set of learning objectives and guiding questions designed to focus attention on key concepts, evidence-based reasoning, and data interpretation.

Discussions are conducted in a student-led format. Instructors act to provide additional clarity, address misconceptions, and gently guide focused conversation to maximize

participation and achieve learning objectives. This approach emphasizes active learning, encourages peer engagement, and supports critical thinking skills.

Accompanying the discussion manual, a participation evaluation rubric is provided to facilitate transparent grading and encourage participation. The rubric clearly defines grading criteria and requirements corresponding to numeric scores of 1, 3, or 5. Following the discussion, students will first complete a self-evaluation of their participation, which is then paired with instructor scoring of student involvement. This ensures student accountability and grading transparency by showing the alignment between student and instructor expectations and encourages metacognitive awareness.

This resource is adaptable across disciplines, course levels, and instructional modalities, and is intended to support equitable, consistent, and meaningful assessment of discussion-based learning. A structured manual for in-class discussions, the participation evaluation rubric, and STEM-focused case study examples are provided in this resource.

Facilitation Guide for Student-led Discussion & Participation Evaluation Rubric

Learning Objectives

1. Increase student metacognitive awareness and educational accountability
 2. Gain experience public-speaking and engaging with peers
 3. Practice data interpretation, critical thinking, and active learning
 4. Relate real-world reports to class lecture material
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Educational Context

Course Type: The discussion guide and participation evaluation rubric were developed for STEM-based case studies, but can be applied to other fields, scholarly material (i.e. journal articles, systemic reviews, book chapters), or education levels.

Class Size: Ideal for class sizes of 8-16 students but can be adaptable to larger class sizes by conducting discussions in two smaller groups (i.e. 30 students, two groups of 15).

Delivery Mode: Ideal for in-person discussion classes but may be adaptable to online or hybrid class formats.

Time Required: Discussion class sessions were designed for 2hr time blocks.

Description of the Instructional Activity

Pre-Class Preparation: The case study, learning objectives, and discussion questions are available to students one week in advance of the class discussion. The lectures prior to the discussion session provide the necessary information and introductory material required to comprehend and analyze the case study.

Instructor Preparation: Instructors will familiarize themselves with the case study and answer the discussion questions prior to the class discussion. Instructors may note specific expectations under each learning objective to ensure the class is focused.

Student Preparation: Students will read the case study and answer the corresponding questions prior to the class discussion. In addition, students should note key concepts related to the learning objectives and practice interpreting any data figures, tables, or medical assessments. Students are expected to have reviewed the related lecture material to establish a base of knowledge and encourage active participation.

Materials Required: Case study with paired discussion questions and learning objectives. Lecture notes or slides. Access to the internet to answer any questions that may arise during reading.

In-Class Discussion Protocol

- 1. Introduction / Framing: (5 minutes)** Upon arrival, students are presented with the self-evaluation rubric clearly stating the participation criteria to achieve a score of 1, 3, or 5 for the discussion. Instructors ensure each student has a copy of the case study to reference during the discussion. Additionally, instructors confirm that each student has answered the discussion questions on their own to the best of their ability.
- 2. Small-Group Analysis: (10-15 minutes)** The class will break into small groups of 2-3 students to review the case study. This discussion should include a general summary of the report, the key findings, interpretation of results, and how the case relates back to the lecture material. This small group analysis also gives the students time to ask questions of their peers, compare interpretations, and feel comfortable with discussing the material in a more intimate setting.
- 3. Whole-Class Discussion: (45 minutes – 1.5hrs)** This portion of the class will be evaluated by both instructor and student to provide a participation score by the end of the class discussion. All participation is voluntary; however, participation is encouraged as it is a component of the grade for the course. The instructor should monitor the discussion to ensure each student has equal opportunity to participate and achieve the maximum participation score of 5. Students will begin the discussion by providing a summary of the case for the class. Discussion questions will be answered in a natural flow with the class discussion. Additional questions or thought-provoking comments are strongly encouraged to foster critical thinking skills. The instructor should ensure that each question is covered and learning objectives are achieved. The instructor's role is to gently guide the discussion to keep the conversation focused and should be available to clarify misconceptions or points of confusion.
- 4. Synthesis / Reflection: (15 minutes)** Following the discussion, students will have time to self-reflect by filling out the participation evaluation rubric. This will include a numeric score corresponding to their participation, and any comments the student may want the instructor to be aware of. Lastly, each student will complete the 'exit ticket' on the back of the self-evaluation rubric, writing 1-2 questions

related to the covered topics that week that might require further clarification or may be beneficial to review for the course final exam. After each student has completed their self-assessment and exited the classroom, the instructor will collect the rubrics and record student scores. The grade for that discussion will then be a cumulative score of both the student and instructor participation points.

Instructor Facilitation Notes

- **Strategies for promoting equitable participation:** Public speaking is a critical skill for students to develop as they progress through their education. In open-format class discussions, students may have different levels of comfort with contributing to the conversation. This can bias the participation to favor a handful of students that are comfortable in these settings. It is important for the instructor to monitor the students to allow for equal opportunities to participate. Some suggestions include:
 - Having students raise their hands so the instructor may call on each student equally. This does not take away from the student-led format but may help to equalize participation.
 - Include opportunities to participate beyond speaking in front of the class. Consider having drawing activities to illustrate key concepts or relate the case study to lecture material. Here, students can volunteer to draw on the board and provide a summary of the drawing with a partner to the larger class.
 - Gently encourage certain students to speak up in pairs. For example: “John and Kate, you both were discussing this point in our small breakout groups, would you share that thought with the class?” This may help students feel less pressured if there is a partner sharing the spotlight.
 - Provide positive and constructive feedback on the evaluation rubric to encourage future participation. For example: “Your comment about X was insightful. I’d love to hear more of your thoughts during next week’s discussion, and I encourage you to lead with answering one of the questions for the class.”

Participation Evaluation Rubric

Overview

Actively participating in discussions with student colleagues and self-reflection are two key components of personal and educational growth. The Participation Evaluation Rubric was developed to encourage students to take accountability for their participation using transparent grading criteria. The rubric allows students and instructors to track participation points and encourages metacognitive awareness by asking students to reflect on their strengths/weaknesses that week or write down additional thoughts about the discussion. Each discussion session is worth a total of 10 points; up to 5 points obtained from student self-scoring and up to 5 points obtained from the instructor score. The requirements to achieve a score of 1, 3, or 5 are clearly outlined in the rubric.

Rubric Criteria and Performance Levels

Score = 1

- You attended class
- You did not speak or contribute to the class discussion

Score = 3

- You attended class
- You added to the discussion by **agreeing/disagreeing** with the professor and/or a student colleague or you **asked a basic question** (or more) about the topic that could easily have been answered through more careful reading of the material
- You did not add any additional revealing thoughts or explanations to the discussion

Score = 5

- You attended class
- You **actively participated** in the discussion through **voicing new thoughts**, opinions and/or questions on the topic and demonstrated your ability to think by **adding to and elevating the level of discussion** following your comment.

Appendices

Appendix A: Participation Evaluation Rubric

Appendix B: Sample Case Study Prompt and Student Instructions Handout_1

Appendix C: Sample Case Study Prompt and Student Instructions Handout_2

Attribution

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